

CARBON NANOTUBE GRAFTED CARBON FIBERS: OPTIMUM PROCESS

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SUMMARY

To improve the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) of carbon fibers with polymer matrix, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were grafted on the carbon fibers through several processes including desizing of carbon fibers, introductions of a functional group and iron nanoparticles, and chemical vapour deposition (CVD) for CNT growth. The current study was focused on the process optimum that can ensure specific distribution and size of grafted CNTs and minimize damages of carbon fibers during the grafting process. Single fiber composites were prepared to investigate the improvement of IFSS due to the grafted CNTs on the carbon fibers.

Keywords: carbon nanotube, carbon fiber, interfacial strength, optimization, thin-ply composite

INTRODUCTION

Due to their stiffness, strength and lightness, high-performance carbon fiber have been widely used for structural composites in various area such as airplanes, satellites, and sport goods [1]. There are several factors determining the performance of carbon fiber composites. These include carbon fiber itself, matrix precursors, fiber-matrix interface and processing conditions [2]. Since the mechanical properties of carbon fibers developed so far were saturated, the fiber-matrix interface control can be considered as an effective means of further improving the mechanical properties of carbon composites.

Recently it was suggested that CNT grafting onto carbon fibers may be a new method of modifying the interface and increasing IFSS [3]. There are two issues for this research. One is the optimum distribution and size of grafted CNTs. The other is a process condition that can realize such distribution and sizes. The former can be determined by a theoretical study, e.g., calculation of the shear stiffness of matrix including CNTs upon shear stress applied. Systematic experimental studies may resolve the latter issue.

This study was aimed to make process charts that can control the distribution and sizes of grafted CNTs. Each process for grafting CNTs was scrutinized experimentally to make relationships between process conditions and their outcomes. Then, an optimum condition was sought that can grow CNTs on carbon fibers with designed distribution and size without deteriorating the mechanical properties of carbon fibers.

EXPERIMENTS

Materials

High strength (HT) carbon fibers with sizing agents and surface treatment were used as the substrate of CNT growth. The fibers were cleaned in distilled water by ultrasonic vibration. The sizing agents on the surface of the fibers were removed using a heat treatment because they may interact with afterward processes such as oxidation, introduction of iron nanoparticles, CVD, etc.

Surface treatment of carbon fiber

It is difficult to directly grow CNT on the surface of carbon fiber because the outer layer of carbon fibers is more ordered than the core. The carbon fibers were modified to have oxygen on the surface of carbon fibers by a dry method that can increase the surface chemical reactivity. The actual treatment time was varied to control the density of active functional group at 500 °C in air condition. FT-IR spectroscopy and BET adsorption analysis was adopted to confirm the surface treatment. For quantitative analysis, scanning electron microscope (SEM) images taken after catalysts treatment were used of identifying active functional groups introduced.

Introduction of catalysts

Catalysts for CNT growth were introduced on the modified surface of carbon fibers using an immersion method. First carbon fibers were immersed into iron sulfate solution. Then, the reduction of the catalysts was conducted to form iron nanoparticles for 5 minutes before CNT growth. The relationship between concentration of catalysts and nanoparticles on the fiber surface was determined using SEM images.

CNT growth by CVD

CNTs were synthesized and grafted on the fiber surface by CVD process using a tubular furnace. The growth of CNTs was controlled using variable time at 750 °C in the carrier gases (Ar and H₂). The distribution and sizes of CNTs on the surface of carbon fiber were investigated using SEM images.

Single fiber composites

Before used for the composites, carbon fibers underwent several processes so that their microstructure and thus mechanical properties including tensile strength may be changed. An optimum condition that can minimize the deterioration of the tensile strength was chosen. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) was then investigated by preparing single fiber composites. The IFSS was estimated using Kelly-Tyson model [4] through single fiber fragmentation tests.

DISCUSSIONS

Surface treatment of carbon fiber

Active sites attracting catalysts for CNT growth are required to graft CNTs on the surface of carbon fibers. The oxidation process was confirmed for this purpose by BET analysis (see Table 1). The BET surface area was increased after desizing, which may be due to the exposure of carbon fiber surface. The surface treatment (oxidation process) increases BET surface area significantly because it may remove weak outer layers of carbon fibers and thus increase surface active groups [5].

Table 1. BET surface area of carbon fibers.

	Row CF	Desized CF	Surface treated CF
BET surface area (m ² /g)	0.6075	1.6768	10.1538

Figure 1. FT-IR spectrum of carbon fibers according to treated time.

The qualitative analysis for the active sites was conducted using FT-IR spectrum (see Figure 1). The peak intensities at 1288cm⁻¹ and 1714cm⁻¹ were decreased after the desizing, implying that the sizing agent may include some functional groups associated with O-C=O and C=O. Other peaks at 1275cm⁻¹, 1470cm⁻¹, 1530cm⁻¹, 1687cm⁻¹ and 1744cm⁻¹ were increased in intensity as the surface treatment time was increased. This may be due to active sites associated with N-C=O, C=O and quinones on the carbon fiber surface. The peak locations were a little moved after the desizing and the surface treatment, e.g., the peaks at 1275 cm⁻¹ and 1288 cm⁻¹ were included on the same band. This indicates that the active sites introduced by the surface treatment were different

from existing sites on the carbon fiber, confirming that the current surface treatment introduced the active sites.

Figure 2. Morphological change of carbon fibers after catalyst introduction. (a) no treatment, (b) desizing only, (c) desizing and surface treatment for 15 mins, (d) desizing and surface treatment for 90 mins.

A quantitative analysis of active sites is required because they may determine the distribution of CNTs grown during CVD process. Although the existence of active sites was confirmed by BET and FT-IR analysis, their amount can not be determined because BET surface area is not proportional exactly to apparent active surface area. Iron ions, which are introduced for CNT growth, can be used to figure out the distribution of the active functional groups on the carbon fiber surface (see Figure 2). The surface roughness was decreased as the surface treatment time was increased by more iron ions on the surface. The distribution of the active sites may be estimated by measuring the amount of irons introduced on the carbon fiber surface using EDS analysis.

Introduction of catalysts

It has been known that the size of catalyst nanoparticles determines the diameter of CNT [6]. In turn, the size of nanoparticles is influenced by the catalyst ions on the surface of carbon fiber. In this study, the catalyst ion in amount was controlled by varying the solution concentration at a constant immersion time. Figure 3 shows the results obtained from two different concentrations. 0.5M concentration seems high enough to fill the grooves between fibers, while some grooves are observed in 0.1M. The effect of the catalyst concentration on the nanoparticle size is under study using more systematic experiments and presented at the conference.

Figure 3. Morphological changes of carbon fibers according to the concentration of catalyst solution. (a) 0.1 M and (b) 0.5 M iron sulfate solution.

CNT growth by CVD

The uniform CNTs were synthesized on the carbon fiber without impurities such as soot as shown in Figure 4. CNT was grown larger than the diameter of carbon fiber. Since too tall CNTs entangle each other and hinder resin infiltration between them, the size of CNTs should be controlled. Since CVD time may determine it, a quantitative relationship between time and size need to be established and included in this research scope.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Morphologies of carbon fiber. (a) before and (b) after CVD process for CNT growth and.

Optimized process

The distribution and size (length and diameter) of grafted CNTs may determine the IFSS of carbon fiber reinforced composites. Furthermore each process for CNT grafting influences the microstructure of carbon fibers and change their mechanical properties. As a result, there are two optimum problems for the best performance of CNT grafting. The first optimum may be determined theoretically, which is in progress. The second optimum can be sought by measuring the mechanical properties of carbon fibers undergoing each process. Figure 5 shows the strength variation of carbon fibers according to each grafting process, clearly indicating that the process optimum should be determined to minimize the destruction of the graphite structure on the surface of carbon fiber.

Figure 5. Tensile strength of carbon fiber for each process
 1 - raw CF, 2 - surface treated CF, 3 - catalyst introduced CF, and 4 - CNT grafted CF

Single fiber composites

The research into single fiber composites from CNT grafted carbon fibers is in progress and will be presented at the conference.

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